

Refinement of Fractional Weddle's-Type Inequalities via Tempered Fractional Integrals

Asra Ahmad¹, Hüseyin Budak², Bilal Ahmad³, Asia Shehzadi⁴, Wali Haider⁵

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Pakistan

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

³School of Mathematics and Computational Science, Xiangtan University, Xiangtan, 411105, China

⁴School of Mathematics and Statistics, Central South University, Changsha 410083, China

⁵School of Mathematics and Statistics, Shaanxi Normal University, Xi'an, Shaanxi, 710119, China

Corresponding author: haiderwali416@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: 0009-0008-7864-3635

Second Author: 0000-0001-8843-955X

Third Author: 0009-0002-8603-0421

Fourth Author: 0009-0005-1101-5536

Fifth Author: 0009-0001-7065-2755

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.18011928

Abstract

Fractional calculus generalizes classical differentiation and integration of arbitrary order. It offers practical analytical tools for describing complex phenomena exhibiting memory and nonlocal behavior. This investigation introduces unique inequalities for convex functions employing tempered fractional integrals, focusing on Weddle's type inequalities. A significant equality is formulated within the framework of tempered fractional integrals. Based on this identity, we develop various Weddle-type inequalities for differentiable convex mappings connected with tempered fractional integrals. These mappings extend the applicability of fractional calculus by extending classical notions and presenting further insight into the behavior of convex functions. We attain distinctive types of Weddle's type inequalities by involving key mathematical tools such as Holder's and power mean inequality, enhancing the implementation of these inequalities in diverse mathematical domains.

Keywords: Weddle's formula type inequality, convex function, tempered fractional integrals

1 Introduction and Motivation

By adding derivatives and integrals of fractional/non-integer orders, fractional calculus (FC), which was originally presented in 1695 through the correspondence between Leibniz and the Marquis de l'Hospital, expands on classical calculus. Later, mathematicians like Euler, Liouville, and Riemann developed the theory, and during the 19th century, it was acknowledged as a crucial tool in both theoretical and applied mathematics. FC is unique because of its non-local nature, which makes it particularly helpful for explaining memory and inherited effects in materials and systems. FC has become an increasingly important tool for representing non-standard occurrences in various fields, such as geometry, dynamics, and fractional differential equations [23, 12, 10]. These days, it is used in viscoelasticity, bioengineering, control theory, and acoustics [1]. Foundational works like those by Samko, Kilbas, and Marichev (1993) and Podlubny (1999), which allow the study of the complex and unpredictable ways that natural systems function, have solidified its place in science and engineering.

The well-known Riemann-Liouville (RL) fractional integrals are listed as follows:

Definition 1.1 (See [15, 11]). Presume $F \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$, the RL fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$, expressed as:

$$J_{\Theta+}^{\alpha} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\Theta}^{\varkappa} (\varkappa - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa > \Theta$$

and

$$J_{\rho-}^{\alpha} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varkappa}^{\rho} (\kappa - \varkappa)^{\alpha-1} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa < \rho.$$

Definition 1.2. The Gamma function, as described in [7], is described using the subsequent integral expression.

$$\Gamma(\chi) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\kappa} \kappa^{\chi-1} d\kappa, \quad \text{Re}(\chi) > 0.$$

See references [21, 2, 8] for a more thorough explanation of RL fractional integrals. However, fractional integral inequalities are crucial for practical mathematics and differential equation analysis. A key concept in mathematics since ancient times is mathematical inequality, which compares two values or expressions to show their relationships or relative magnitudes. Convex functions are closely related to the theory of inequality; several famous inequalities, such as Hermite–Hadamard, Simpson, Newton, Euler–Maclaurin, and Boole’s type inequalities, have been developed for convex functions. Convexity serves as a reliable tool for studying inequalities, laying the groundwork for using geometric and analytical techniques to verify these conclusions. Convex function analysis and inequality analysis are closely related, with each impacting the development of the other. Please refer to [13, 3, 25] and the sources listed therein for more details on convexity and Newton-type inequalities associated with convex differentiable functions.

The tempered fractional integral was initially studied in this subject by Buschman [4]. Following this, further comprehensive contributions were made by Liu et al. [16] and Meerschaert et al. [20]. A prominent subfield of fractional calculus called tempered fractional calculus

finds a special intersection between weighted fractional calculus and fractional calculus with analytic kernels [9]. It can be considered an extension of fractional calculus due to its wide application and importance. Its significance is demonstrated by its rediscovery under many titles, such as significant fractional calculus [9, 5] and generalized proportional fractional calculus [14]. The next section reviews the essential preparations that form the basis of our key conclusions.

Definition 1.3 (See [22]). For real values $\alpha > 0$ and $\varkappa, \lambda \geq 0$, the λ -incomplete gamma function is identified as:

$$\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \varkappa) := \int_0^{\varkappa} \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\kappa} d\kappa.$$

$\lambda = 1$ corresponds to the incomplete gamma function [6]:

$$\Upsilon(\alpha, \varkappa) := \int_0^{\varkappa} \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\kappa} d\kappa.$$

Where, $0 < \alpha < \infty$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

Remark 1.1 (See [22]). For the real values $\alpha > 0$ and $\varkappa, \lambda \geq 0$, we gain

$$\text{I. } \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha, 1) = \int_0^1 \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho-\Theta)\kappa} d\kappa = \frac{1}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha}} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \Theta).$$

$$\text{II. } \int_0^1 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha, \varkappa) d\varkappa = \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha, \rho-\Theta)}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha}} - \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha+1, \rho-\Theta)}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}.$$

Definition 1.4 (See [17, 21]). Tempered fractional integral operators of order $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$ are presented as:

$$\mathfrak{I}_{\Theta+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\Theta}^{\varkappa} (\varkappa - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varkappa-\kappa)} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa \in [\Theta, \rho]$$

and

$$\mathfrak{I}_{\rho-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varkappa}^{\rho} (\kappa - \varkappa)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\kappa-\varkappa)} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa \in [\Theta, \rho],$$

respectively for $F \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$.

The RL fractional integral equations in Definition 1.1 are obviously comparable if we assume $\lambda = 0$ in Definition 1.4..

Using tempered fractional integral operators, Gul and Yalcin [11] developed Minkowski and Hermite–Hadamard integral inequalities. They displayed a number of integral inequality instances for tempered fractional integrals from earlier research. For more details, interested readers are referred to [23, 24, 26].

Inspired by previous research, we employed tempered fractional integrals to identify some of Boole’s formula-type inequalities in the class of functions whose derivatives are convex functions. This paper examines important mathematical tools such as Holder’s and power mean inequality, enhancing the implementation of these inequalities in diverse mathematical domains. The most important advantage of these inequalities is that, by setting $\lambda = 0$, these inequalities turned into

Riemann–Liouville fractional Boole’s type inequalities. With $\alpha = 1$, the modified inequalities transform into classical Boole’s type inequalities.

The study is broken up into three pieces, the first of which is an introduction and preliminary material that includes basic concepts of fractional calculus and a synopsis of important research in the area. Section 1.1 will establish some results regarding Boole’s type inequality for differentiable convex functions. We also assess Boole’s formula for new mathematical tools such as holder’s inequality and power mean. We summarize our results and potential study opportunities in the last part.

1.1 Main Contributions

Lemma 1.1. If $F : [\Theta, \rho] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function that is absolutely continuous on (Θ, ρ) such that $F' \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$. Then, the following equality is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \\ & - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] = \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \\ & \times \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \right. \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \\ & \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Proof. By acknowledging the essential rules of integration, it is enough to state that

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \\ &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left[\left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) \right]_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \\ &\quad - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \\ &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1)}{5(\rho - \Theta)} F(\Theta) \\ &\quad - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi, \tag{2} \\ I_2 &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{2}{3}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) \\ &\quad - \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$-\frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi. \tag{3}$$

In the same way, we find

$$\begin{aligned} I_3 &= \frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) \\ &\quad - \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}\left(\alpha, \frac{2}{3}\right) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) \\ &\quad - \frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Consequently, we arrive at the subsequent equality by merging (2)-(4)

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 + I_2 + I_3 &= \frac{2}{10(\rho-\Theta)} \left[\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F(\Theta) + 5 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 3 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \left[\int_0^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Similarly

$$\begin{aligned} I_4 + I_5 + I_6 &= -\frac{2}{10(\rho-\Theta)} \left[\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F(\rho) + \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 5 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + 3 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \left[\int_0^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) d\xi \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

By subtracting equalities (5) and (6), then we make the substitutions $\varpi = \frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta$ and $\varpi = \frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho$ for $\xi \in [0, 1]$, it becomes

$$\begin{aligned} &[I_1 + I_2 + I_3 - (I_4 + I_5 + I_6)] \\ &= \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)}{5(\rho-\Theta)} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha+1}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\Theta) \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Multiplying both sides of (7) by $\frac{\rho-\Theta}{4\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)}$, the equality (1) is obtained. □

Theorem 1.1. If all the conditions in Lemma 1.1 are accomplished and $|F'|$ is convex on $[\Theta, \rho]$, then one can prove the following inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} (\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda)) [|\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)|], \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi, \\ \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi, \\ \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By referencing Lemma 1.1 and leveraging the convexity of $|\mathbf{F}'|$, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathbf{F}(\Theta) + 5\mathbf{F} \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6} \right) + \mathbf{F} \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3} \right) + 6\mathbf{F} \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right) + \mathbf{F} \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3} \right) + 5\mathbf{F} \left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6} \right) + \mathbf{F}(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathbf{F}(\rho) + \mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathbf{F}(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \times \left| \mathbf{F}' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} \Theta \right) - \mathbf{F}' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} \rho \right) \right| d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathbf{F}' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} \Theta \right) - \mathbf{F}' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} \rho \right) \right| d\xi \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathbf{F}' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} \Theta \right) - \mathbf{F}' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} \rho \right) \right| d\xi \right] \quad (9) \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \times \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\Theta)| + \frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\rho)| \right) d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \\ & \quad \times \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\Theta)| + \frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\rho)| \right) d\xi \left. \right] \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda \left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \\ & \quad \times \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\Theta)| + \frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\rho)| \right) d\xi \left. \right] \\ & = \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} (\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda)) [|\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)|]. \end{aligned}$$

We have reached the conclusion of the proof of Theorem 1.1. □

Remark 1.2. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.1, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(\rho-\Theta)^\alpha} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^\alpha F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^\alpha F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho-\Theta)}{4} (\Delta_1(\alpha, 0) + \Delta_2(\alpha, 0) + \Delta_3(\alpha, 0)) [|F'(\Theta)| + |F'(\rho)|], \end{aligned}$$

which is derived in [18].

Remark 1.3. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.1, then we gain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho-\Theta} \int_\Theta^\rho F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \leq \frac{13(\rho-\Theta)}{450} [|F'(\Theta)| + |F'(\rho)|], \end{aligned}$$

which is proved in [27].

Theorem 1.2. If all the conditions in Lemma 1.1 are accomplished and $|F'|^q, q > 1$ is convex on $[\Theta, \rho]$, then the subsequent inequality is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\gamma_1(\alpha, p) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 7|F'(\Theta)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 7|F'(\rho)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \gamma_2(\alpha, p) \left\{ \left(\frac{3|F'(\rho)|^q + 5|F'(\Theta)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|F'(\Theta)|^q + 5|F'(\rho)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right], \tag{10} \end{aligned}$$

where $p^{-1} + q^{-1} = 1,$

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) &= \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \gamma_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) &= \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \gamma_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) &= \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By applying Hölder’s inequality (9), it becomes

$$\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \Big| \\
 & \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\
 & \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \quad \times \left. \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

By exploiting the convexity $|F'|^q$, we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \Big| \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \\
 & \quad \times \left[\gamma_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 & \quad + \gamma_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \Big] \\
 & \quad + \gamma_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \Big] \\
 & \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\gamma_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad + \left. \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + \gamma_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + \gamma_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \Big]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\gamma_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 11|F'(\Theta)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 11|F'(\rho)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ &\quad + \gamma_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 3|F'(\Theta)|^q}{12} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 3|F'(\rho)|^q}{12} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &\quad \left. + \gamma_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{5|F'(\rho)|^q + 7|F'(\Theta)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|F'(\Theta)|^q + 7|F'(\rho)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

We have successfully concluded the proof for Theorem 1.2. □

Remark 1.4. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.2, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(\rho - \Theta)^\alpha} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^\alpha F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^\alpha F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha(\rho - \Theta)}{4} \left[\gamma_1^p(\alpha, 0) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 11|F'(\Theta)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 11|F'(\rho)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ &\quad + \gamma_2^p(\alpha, 0) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 3|F'(\Theta)|^q}{12} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 3|F'(\rho)|^q}{12} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &\quad \left. + \gamma_3^p(\alpha, 0) \left\{ \left(\frac{5|F'(\rho)|^q + 7|F'(\Theta)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|F'(\Theta)|^q + 7|F'(\rho)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right], \end{aligned}$$

which is derived by Mateen et al. in [18, Theorem 6].

Remark 1.5. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.2, then we gain

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho - \Theta} \int_\Theta^\rho F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \\ &\leq \left[2 \left(\frac{3^{-p-1} 7^p 20^{-2p-1} \left(3^{p+1} \left(\frac{20}{7} \right)^p + 7 \cdot 20^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\ &\quad \times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Psi'(v)|^q + 11|\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Psi'(v)|^q + |\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &\quad + 2^{1-\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{15^{-2p-1} \left(\left(\frac{15}{2} \right)^p + 2^{p+2} 15^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &\quad \times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Psi'(v)|^q + 3|\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|\Psi'(v)|^q + |\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &\quad \left. + 2 \times 3^{-1/p} \left(\frac{20^{-2p-1} \left(\left(\frac{20}{3} \right)^p + 3^{p+2} 20^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Psi'(v)|^q + 11|\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Psi'(v)|^q + |\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\},$$

which is identified in [19, Corollary 3].

Theorem 1.3. If all the conditions in Lemma 1.1 are accomplished and $|F'|^q$, $q \geq 1$ is convex on $[\Theta, \rho]$, then the subsequent inequality is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[(\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_1(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_1(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (S_1(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_1(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + (\Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_2(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_2(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (S_2(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_2(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + (\Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_3(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_3(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (S_3(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_3(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right], \tag{11} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} S_1(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{\xi}{2} d\xi, \\ S_2(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{\xi}{2} d\xi, \\ S_3(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{\xi}{2} d\xi, \\ U_1(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{2 - \xi}{2} d\xi, \\ U_2(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{2 - \xi}{2} d\xi, \\ U_3(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{2 - \xi}{2} d\xi. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Based on Lemma 1.1 and by utilizing the power-mean inequality after considering the modulus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

As $|F'|^q$ is convex on the interval $[\Theta, \rho]$, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad + \left. \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof of Theorem 1.3 has been finalized. □

Remark 1.6. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.3, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(\rho-\Theta)^\alpha} \left[\mathcal{J}_{(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2})^+}^\alpha F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2})^-}^\alpha F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho-\Theta)}{4} \left[(\Delta_1(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_1(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_1(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + (S_1(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_1(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + (\Delta_2(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_2(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_2(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + (S_2(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_2(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + (\Delta_3(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_3(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_3(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + (S_3(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_3(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

which is derived in [18].

Remark 1.7. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.3, then we gain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho-\Theta} \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \\
 & \leq (\rho-\Theta) \left[\left(\frac{29}{3600} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{577|F'(\rho)|^q + 4643|F'(\Theta)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{577|F'(\Theta)|^q + 4643|F'(\rho)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{17}{1800} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{37|F'(\rho)|^q + 133|F'(\Theta)|^q}{18000} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{37|F'(\Theta)|^q + 133|F'(\rho)|^q}{18000} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{41}{3600} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{3311|F'(\rho)|^q + 4069|F'(\Theta)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3311|F'(\Theta)|^q + 4069|F'(\rho)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

which is established in [19].

1.2 Future Research Directions

This work presents unique Boole’s formula-type inequalities involving tempered fractional integrals for single-time differentiable convex functions. Initially, we established an integral identity associated with tempered fractional integrals. Subsequently, we verified novel Boole’s formula

inequalities for differentiable convex functions. The bounds of Boole's formula can be ascertained using the inequalities discussed in this study. These inequalities can be helpful in the estimation of errors that occur when functions are approximated using polynomials or other simplified functions in approximation theory. Concerning integral inequalities, the conclusions of this work are crucial and offer numerous possibilities for new researchers to investigate further extensions and the consequences of these results in other mathematical disciplines. This study has important implications for future research on generalized fractional integrals, convexity, s -convexity, and equations with higher-order derivatives.

References

- [1] George A Anastassiou. Generalized fractional calculus. *Studies in Systems, Decision and Control*, 305, 2021.
- [2] Boris Baeumer and Mark M Meerschaert. Tempered stable lévy motion and transient super-diffusion. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, 233(10):2438–2448, 2010.
- [3] HÜSEYİN Budak, H Kara, MZ Sarikaya, and ME Kiriş. New extensions of the hermite-hadamard inequalities involving riemann-liouville fractional integrals. *Miskolc Mathematical Notes*, 21(2):665–678, 2020.
- [4] RG Buschman. Decomposition of an integral operator by use of mikusiński calculus. *SIAM Journal on Mathematical Analysis*, 3(1):83–85, 1972.
- [5] Jianxiong Cao, Changpin Li, and YangQuan Chen. On tempered and substantial fractional calculus. In *2014 IEEE/ASME 10th International Conference on Mechatronic and Embedded Systems and Applications (MESA)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2014.
- [6] Jianhua Chen and Xianjiu Huang. Some new inequalities of simpson's type for s -convex functions via fractional integrals. *Filomat*, 31(15):4989–4997, 2017.
- [7] Leonhard Euler. On transcendental progressions that is, those whose general terms cannot be given algebraically. *Commentarii academiae scientiarum Petropolitanae*, 1738(5):36–57, 1999.
- [8] Arran Fernandez and Hafiz Muhammad Fahad. Weighted fractional calculus: a general class of operators. *Fractal and Fractional*, 6(4):208, 2022.
- [9] Rudolf Friedrich, Frank Jenko, Adrian Baule, and S Eule. Anomalous diffusion of inertial, weakly damped particles. *Physical review letters*, 96(23):230601, 2006.
- [10] Rudolf Gorenflo and Francesco Mainardi. Fractional calculus: integral and differential equations of fractional order. In *Fractals and fractional calculus in continuum mechanics*, pages 223–276. Springer, 1997.

- [11] Erdal Gül and Abdüllatif Yalçın. Some novel estimations of hadamard type inequalities for different kinds of convex functions via tempered fractional integral operator. *Filomat*, 38(10):3683–3690, 2024.
- [12] Abd-Allah Hyder and MA Barakat. Novel improved fractional operators and their scientific applications. *Advances in Difference Equations*, 2021(1):389, 2021.
- [13] Sabah Iftikhar, Poom Kumam, and Samet Erden. Newton’s-type integral inequalities via local fractional integrals. *Fractals*, 28(03):2050037, 2020.
- [14] Fahd Jarad, Thabet Abdeljawad, and Jehad Alzabut. Generalized fractional derivatives generated by a class of local proportional derivatives. *The European Physical Journal Special Topics*, 226(16):3457–3471, 2017.
- [15] AA Kilbas. Theory and applications of fractional differential equations. *North-Holland Mathematics Studies*, 204, 2006.
- [16] Can Li, Weihua Deng, and Lijing Zhao. Well-posedness and numerical algorithm for the tempered fractional ordinary differential equations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1501.00376*, 2015.
- [17] Ruyi Liu and Zhen Wu. Well-posedness of a class of two-point boundary value problems associated with ordinary differential equations. *Advances in Difference Equations*, 2018(1):54, 2018.
- [18] A. Mateen, H. Budak, W. Haider, and A. Shehzadi. Innovative Weddle’s formula type inequalities using Riemann–Liouville fractional integral with numerical analysis. *Submitted*, Submitted.
- [19] Abdul Mateen, Zhiyue Zhang, Hüseyin Budak, and Serap Özcan. Some novel inequalities of weddle’s formula type for riemann–liouville fractional integrals with their applications to numerical integration. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 192:115973, 2025.
- [20] M. M. Meerschaert and F. Sabzikar. Tempered fractional Brownian motion. *Statistics and Probability Letters*, 83:2269–2275, 2013.
- [21] Mark M Meerschaert, Farzad Sabzikar, Mantha S Phanikumar, and Aklilu Zeleke. Tempered fractional time series model for turbulence in geophysical flows. *Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment*, 2014(9):P09023, 2014.
- [22] Pshtiwan Othman Mohammed, Mehmet Zeki Sarikaya, and Dumitru Baleanu. On the generalized hermite–hadamard inequalities via the tempered fractional integrals. *Symmetry*, 12(4):595, 2020.
- [23] Humberto Rafeiro and Stefan Samko. Fractional integrals and derivatives: mapping properties. *Fractional Calculus and Applied Analysis*, 19(3):580–607, 2016.
- [24] Stefan G Samko. Fractional integrals and derivatives. *Theory and applications*, 1993.

- [25] Mehmet Zeki Sarikaya, Erhan Set, Hatice Yaldiz, and Nagihan Başak. Hermite–hadamard’s inequalities for fractional integrals and related fractional inequalities. *Mathematical and computer modelling*, 57(9-10):2403–2407, 2013.
- [26] Hari M Srivastava and Robert George Buschman. Convolution integral equations: with special function kernels. (*No Title*), 1977.
- [27] M. Toseef, Z. Zhang, H. Budak, S. I. Butt, and X. Liu. Error bounds of Weddle’s formula for various classes of functions with their applications and numerical analysis. *ResearchGate Preprint*, 2024. Submitted August 2024.